

MEASUREMENT OF PROCESS-INDUCED STRAINS BY FIBRE BRAGG GRATING OPTICAL SENSOR IN RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

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SUMMARY

Process-induced strains were measured using fibre optic sensors in composite panels manufactured by resin transfer moulding. The sensors captured a strain variation during the cool-down related to the debonding of the composite from the mould. The measured tool-part interaction was simulated with the finite element method using contact constraints.

Keywords: Residual strains, Tool-part interaction, Fibre Bragg grating optic sensor, Resin transfer moulding

INTRODUCTION

Residual strains and stresses are one of the major issues while manufacturing composite structures as they can lead to strength reduction, cracks and delamination, and dimensional variability. Strain gages were used to measure the strain development throughout the cure cycle [1, 2]. However, it is difficult to embed the strain gages into the composite laminate and they are usually mounted on the tool. Alternatively, fibre optic sensors appear to be an interesting method to measure the development of the residual strains in-situ during composite manufacturing [3-11], as well as the material transition (gel point, glass transition) [6] or the degree-of-cure [12]. Their advantage over strain gages is that they can be easily integrated in the composite at the preforming stage of the manufacturing. Small and non intrusive, they have also a minimal impact on the mechanical properties of the composite. Different kind of fibre optic sensors are used, such as fibre Bragg grating (FBG) sensors [4-6, 10, 11], extrinsic Fabry-Perot interferometric (EFPI) sensors [3, 7, 9, 12] or FBG/EFPI hybrid sensors [8]. In this study, FBG sensors were used to measure the development of internal strain in a composite laminate manufactured by Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM), as the cure progresses. The measured strains were then compared to finite element analyses modelling the RTM process. The effect of the tool-part interaction was investigated using different boundary conditions at the composite/mould interface.

EXPERIMENTS

RTM procedure

Radial injections were carried out at constant pressure in a rectangular steel mould to manufacture carbon/epoxy laminates with a 50% fibre volume fraction and the following dimensions: 34.5 cm x 24.5 cm x 0.2 cm. Six heating cartridges on each side of the mould (top and bottom) were used to apply the desired cure cycle. The mould surface was treated with release agent (Frekote 770-NC) and flexible silicone joints were used to seal the mould. Five plies of 5-harness satin G30-500 6k carbon fabric [13, 14] were stacked with the following layup [(0/90)(90/0)(0/90)(0/90)(90/0)]. The preform was debulked 30 minutes under vacuum to remove the eventual entrapped air. Once the preform was placed into the mould, the mould was closed and the system was preheated at 180°C prior the resin injection. The CYCOM 890RTM one-part epoxy resin [15] was preheated at 80°C in the injector to reach its optimal viscosity and injected in the mould with 0.35MPa pressure difference. The typical cure cycle of the CYCOM 890RTM epoxy resin was used: 2 hours isotherm at 180°C followed by a cool down by natural convection.

FBG sensors

A Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor is an optical fibre with a periodic modification of the core refractive index along the fibre. When a source of light is connected to the FBG sensor, only a narrow-band of the light is back-reflected around the Bragg wavelength λ_B , given by [16]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda_B \quad (1)$$

where n is the effective refractive index of the core and Λ_B is the grating period.

Any change in the optical fibre properties which varies the grating period or the refractive index, such as strain or temperature, will then change the Bragg wavelength. The Bragg wavelength shift $\Delta\lambda_B$ can be related to the applied strain ε , and temperature T by Eq.1 as follows:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = \left\{ 1 + \left[\frac{1}{n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial \varepsilon} \right]_T \right\} \varepsilon_{tot} + \left\{ \alpha_f + \left[\frac{1}{n} \frac{\partial n}{\partial T} \right]_\varepsilon \right\} \Delta T = K_\varepsilon \varepsilon_{tot} + K_T \Delta T \quad (2)$$

where K_ε and K_T are the strain and temperature sensitivities of the FBG sensor and α_f is the fibre's coefficient of thermal expansion, ε_{tot} is the total strain experienced by the host material, including the mechanical and thermal strains and ΔT is the temperature variation.

In this work, the FBG sensors were provided by Technica SA. Their initial wavelength was 1562 ± 0.5 nm with a bandwidth inferior to 0.3 nm. Their strain sensitivity K_ε and temperature sensitivity K_T were $7.7 \times 10^{-7} \mu\varepsilon^{-1}$ and $6.92 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ respectively. As the curing temperature of the composite was 180°C, the FBG sensors were preconditioned 24 hours at 200°C in an oven before use. The preconditioning or pre-annealing assures the thermal stability of the Bragg wavelength with temperature [17]. The initial optical fibre wavelength, λ_{B0} , was recorded after the preconditioning and prior the embedding in the laminate. For each laminate, three FBG sensors were positioned at the center of the laminate, through the thickness of the laminate, at the bottom surface, middle and top surface, as shown in Figure 1. A thermocouple type K was also placed in the mould cavity to monitor the temperature of the composite part inside the mould. An optical

sensing interrogator sm125-500 from Micron Optics was used to monitor the variation of the FBG wavelength λ_B during the entire cure.

Figure 1: FBG sensors position in the laminate

Measured in-plane strains

Figure 2 presents the wavelength variation of the three FBG sensors during the entire cure cycle. First, the wavelength increased as the mould heated up and the sensors expanded with the temperature. Then a decrease in the wavelength was observed at the injection due to the temperature gradient between the mould and the resin. As the resin was colder than the mould, the sensors contracted when the resin reached them. During the isotherm, the wavelength remained constant and it finally decreased during cool down. A wavelength discontinuity was observed at around 250 minutes in the cool down which corresponds to a separation of the composite from the mould, as explained in the following. Using Eq.2, the total strain variation in the laminate during cure was calculated and plotted in Figure 3. Before the resin injection, the FBG sensor is not bonded to the dry fibres. Therefore, the strain occurring in the fabric might not be totally transferred to the FBG sensor. Thus the strains were then set to zero at the beginning of the injection. However, negative strains were noticed in the composite after the closing of the mould that could be related to the preform compaction. Overall, the composite remained in compression during the cure. Small compressive strains were introduced in the laminate at the injection (around $-50 \mu\epsilon$). Then the strain remained almost constant during the two hour isotherm at 180°C . Since the FBG sensors captured the in-plane strains, the resin more important out-of-plane shrinkage was not clearly observable. During the cool down, a strain discontinuity was observed at around 250 minutes or 150°C . This behaviour corresponded to the composite plate debonding from the mould due to the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch between the composite and the steel tool. Figure 4, showing the strains as a function of temperature confirmed this observation. The evolution of the strain with the temperature was linear with two different slopes before and after the discontinuity. A slope of $15.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$, corresponding to the CTE of steel, was measured before the discontinuity ($150^\circ\text{C} < T < 180^\circ\text{C}$). The slope changed to $4.46 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ after the discontinuity ($25^\circ\text{C} < T < 150^\circ\text{C}$) which is in the order of magnitude of the coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite with a 50% fibre volume fraction. Thus, during the cool down, the composite followed the thermal contraction of the steel mould until the shear stress at the interface mould/composite becomes too high and the laminate separated from the mould. A similar phenomenon was as well observed for laminate manufactured by the autoclave [4]. At the end of the cool down, the composite remained in compression with the value of the residual strain around $-700 \mu\epsilon$.

Figure 2: FBG sensor relative wavelength variation during the cure cycle

Figure 3: In-situ strain variation during the cure cycle from the injection to the end of the cool down

Figure 4: In-situ strain variation with the temperature during the cure cycle

From these experiments, the maximum shear stress the composite can sustain before debonding can be determined. The laminate shear stress τ is related to the laminate in-plane stress σ , which is related to the composite mechanical strain ε_M by the composite Young's modulus E_C , as follows [1]:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma t}{L_0} = \frac{E_C \varepsilon_M t}{L_0} \quad (3)$$

where t is the laminate thickness and L_0 is the laminate length. Using a micromechanic approach, the in-plane composite modulus was estimated to 60 GPa.

The mechanical strain is the difference between the total strain ε_{tot} measured by the top and bottom FBG sensors and the free thermal expansion ε_{TH} as expressed below:

$$\varepsilon_M = \varepsilon_{tot} - \varepsilon_{TH} = \varepsilon_{tot} - CTE_C \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where CTE_C is the in-plane coefficient of thermal expansion of the composite and ΔT is the temperature variation. CTE_C was determined by analysing the strains measured by the FBG sensors during the laminate post-cure and was estimated to $2.50 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$. Using Eq.3 and Eq.4, the laminate maximum shear stress was then determined to 130 kPa. Using Eq.3, the residual stress in the composite were estimated around -20 MPa at the end of the process.

TOOL-PART INTERACTION MODELLING

The RTM process and the tool-part interaction between the composite and the mould was then investigated numerically using the commercial finite element software ABAQUS and the COMPRO Component Architecture (CCA) subroutine developed by Convergent Manufacturing Technology Inc. The CYCOM 890RTM epoxy resin material property models (cure kinetics, viscosity, chemical shrinkage, glass transition temperature, elastic modulus) developed in previous studies [18, 19] were implemented in the CCA library. The CCA subroutine uses the material models to compute the change in material properties (resin and composite) during the cure. First, a heat transfer analysis was conducted to predict the evolution of the degree of cure of the composite structure. Then, a stress analysis was performed to compute the instantaneous strains, stresses and nodal displacements in the laminate.

Geometry and finite element mesh

A 2 mm thick composite plate and a steel rectangular mould were modelled using the actual dimensions of the RTM mould and the manufactured composite plate. Due to the problem symmetry, only one quarter of the system was analyzed as shown in Figure 5-a. A 1 cm gap between the mould and the composite sides was added to allow the composite part to expand and not exceed the tool boundaries (Figure 5-b). The five plies 5-Harness satin laminate [(0/90)(90/0)(0/90)(0/90)(90/0)] at 50% fibre volume fraction was modelled by ten unidirectional layers with the following layup [0/90/90/0/0/90/0/90/90/0]. In order to account for the fibre waviness, the carbon fibre properties were lower assuming that the fibre yarns have a 70% fibre volume fraction. At 0°, the fibre were oriented in the length of the plate, as shown in Figure 5-c. Ten elements were used for each layer through the composite thickness. Three-dimensional 8-nodes solid elements were used: DC3D8 for the heat transfer analysis and C3D8 for the stress analysis.

Figure 5: Steel mould and composite plate finite element model: a) finite element mesh, b) close-up of the laminate finite element mesh, c) schematic position of the analyzed element

Boundary conditions: displacements, temperature

The displacements were fixed to prevent rigid motion. The top and bottom mould surfaces were fixed in the z-direction in order to simulate the press that keep the cavity thickness constant and the two-part mould fixed in the RTM process. The mould top surface constraint in the z-direction was then removed during the cool down to allow the mould contraction. No initial pressure was applied to the mould or the composite part.

The same cure cycle as the one used during the experiment was used: 120 minutes isotherm at 180°C followed by a cool down to 25°C by natural convection. The temperature field was applied to the top and bottom element layer of the mould to simulate the heating cartridges. The mould was assumed adiabatic during the isotherm. During the cool down, the natural convection was applied by defining a heat transfer coefficient of 10 W/m²°C on the mould external surfaces. In the experiment, the resin was injected at 80°C in a mould preheated at 180°C. Injection simulations using the software PAM-RTM showed that at the end of the injection, once the part was totally impregnated, the average temperature of the composite was around 160°C. Therefore, in the process modelling simulation, the initial composite temperature was set at 160°C to account for this initial temperature gradient and the initial mould temperature was set to the curing temperature at 180°C. Also the preform was assumed completely saturated with resin at the beginning of the simulation. The initial degree of cure of the epoxy resin was set to 0.001 in the curing simulation.

Contact interactions

In the stress analysis, three different types of contact interaction were used to model different behaviours between the laminate and the mould.

Model A: no bonding. It analyzed the behaviour of the composite laminate alone, with no contact constraints. In this analysis, the mould was not modelled and the cure cycle

was applied directly to the laminate. This analysis gives the behaviour of the composite plate in a free standing condition.

Model B: perfect bonding. It investigated the behaviour of a composite laminate perfectly bonded to the mould. This was ensured by having coincident and equivalent nodes at the interface between the composite part and the mould.

Model C: frictional contact. It examined the effect of contact interaction at the interface of the composite plate and the mould. In order to take into account the possible interaction between the mould and the composite part, contact constraints were applied, on the composite surfaces in contact with the mould. Contact constraints were defined as follows: “hard” contact relationships were applied to prevent the transfer of tensile stresses across the interface and minimize the surface interpenetration. A stick-slip behaviour was introduced using the classical isotropic Coulomb friction model, $\tau_{crit} = \mu P$, and a shear stress limit τ_{max} . The Coulomb friction model expresses the critical shear stress τ_{crit} at which the surfaces in contact start to slide as a function of the pressure of contact P and the coefficient of friction μ . By introducing τ_{max} , the sliding is then occurring as soon as the magnitude of the equivalent shear stress reaches the minimum between τ_{max} and μP , $\tau_{crit} = \min(\mu P, \tau_{max})$. The maximum shear stress determined experimentally was used as shear stress limit. From the literature review, the coefficient of friction was set to 0.3 [1].

Results and discussion

For each finite element models, the results were reported at the position A, as shown in Figure 5-c. This position corresponded to the position of the FBG sensors and was representative of the strain variations of the composite structure. As three FBG sensors were positioned in the experimental set-up at the top, mid-thickness and bottom of the laminate, the computed total strains were analyzed similarly at the element centroid of the laminate top, middle and bottom layers. However, as the total strains were very similar for the three positions, only the total strain at the laminate mid-thickness was plotted in the graph for clarity purpose. Similarly, the strain in the mould at the top and bottom interface with the laminate were analysed but only the strain of top of the mould was plotted. The total strains included the thermal and mechanical strains.

Temperature and degree-of-cure

The evolution of the predicted composite temperature followed the applied cure cycle. A negligible cure exotherm was predicted during the isotherm with an increase in temperature inferior to $<1^{\circ}\text{C}$. The gel point occurred at $\alpha_{gel} = 0.7$ in the isotherm part at 69 minutes, and the vitrification happened before the cool down, which means that at the end of the isotherm, the resin was in the glassy state. A maximum degree-of-cure of 0.97 was reached at the end of the cycle.

Strain results

Figure 6 present the evolution of the total in-plane strain for the three different types of tool-part interactions (no bonding, perfect bonding, and frictional contact). First the laminate expanded as its temperature increased from 160°C to 180°C in less than two minutes. A greater expansion was noticed for the *model C* than *model B* with a maximum in-plane strain of $190\ \mu\epsilon$ versus $50\ \mu\epsilon$. This is due to the strong effect of the mould that prevented the composite expansion for the perfect bonding case (*model B*).

After 60 minutes into the cure, a decrease in strain was observed corresponding to the resin shrinkage occurring after the gel point. Then, during the cool down, the temperature decrease led to a decrease in the in-plane strains in the composite. In the case of a perfect bonding, the laminate followed the contraction behaviour of the mould with a final total strain of $-1760 \mu\epsilon$. The free standing laminate (*model A*) contracted less with a final strain of $-550 \mu\epsilon$. For the *model C*, the evolution of the total strain during the cool down was situated in between the one obtained for *model A* and *model B*. Contrary to the experimental results, no strain discontinuity was predicted during the cool down. Nevertheless, during the cool down, the evolution of the predicted strain using frictional contact (*model C*) was similar to the evolution of the measured strain after the discontinuity.

Figure 6: Comparison of the in-plane strain evolution at the laminate mid-thickness for the cure cycle 1 obtained experimentally and numerically in the case of no bonding (*model A*) and perfect bonding (*model B*) and frictional contact (*model C*)

Figure 7: Comparison of the in-plane strain evolution with temperature during the cool down at the laminate mid-thickness obtained experimentally and numerically in the case of no bonding (*model A*), perfect bonding (*model B*) and frictional contact (*model C*)

Table 1: Comparison of the experimental and predicted curve gradients obtained with the different models

	Slope 1 (°C ⁻¹)	Slope 2 (°C ⁻¹)	Temperature at discontinuity (°C)
Experiment	15.3x10 ⁻⁶	4.46x10 ⁻⁶	150
Model A	3.6x10 ⁻⁶	-	-
Model B	12x10 ⁻⁶	-	-
Model C	9.2x10 ⁻⁶	3.4x10 ⁻⁶	144

Figure 7 presents the total in-plane strain evolution with the temperature. The different slopes obtained were summarized in Table 1. Overall, the total strain decreased linearly with the temperature. A slope of $3.6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ was measured in the case of the *model A*, which is in the order of magnitude of the in-plane coefficient of thermal the coefficient of the laminate with a 50% fibre volume fraction as seen previously. For the *model B*, the measured slope was $12 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ corresponding to the CTE of the steel mould. Therefore, in a case of perfect bonding (*model B*), the laminate behaved like the mould and followed its thermal contraction. It can be also noticed that *model A* and *model B* captured the trend of the strain evolution after and before the experimental discontinuity respectively. This confirms that the discontinuity corresponds to a separation of the laminate from the mould. A bilinear curve was noticed for *model C*, when the frictional contact constraints were applied. Two slopes, $9.25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ and $3.40 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$ were measured before and after the inflection respectively. The value after the inflection is similar to the slope obtained in the *model A* and corresponds to the laminate CTE. The value obtained before the inflection is close to the CTE of the mould. Hence, during the cool down, the composite followed the thermal contraction of the steel mould until the shear stress at the interface mould/composite reached the maximum shear stress allowed and the laminate debonded from the mould. The inflection occurred almost at the same temperature as the measured strain discontinuity. From these results, the frictional contact boundary conditions appeared to capture better the evolution of the in-plane composite strain measured by FBG sensors developed during the RTM process.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the in-plane strains developed in the laminate during the RTM process were measured in-situ using FBG sensors. The strains development occurred mainly during the process cool down and led to compressive residual stresses in the laminate. The strain measurement captured also the separation of the laminate from the mould during the cool down, due to the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion between the composite and the steel tool. Before the separation, the laminate withstood a maximum shear stress up to 130 kPa. Three 3D finite element models were then developed to simulate the observed tool-part interaction. Using frictional contact at the interface between the laminate and the mould and the maximum shear stress determined experimentally, the *model C* predicted the debonding of the composite from the mould and described well the strain development in the composite. These results demonstrate the capacity of predicting complex tool-part interactions using contact constraints in finite element analysis.

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